

Hidden owners, hidden crimes:

Why beneficial ownership transparency matters for fisheries enforcement

June 2026

Introduction

Fisheries are central to the socio-economic stability of coastal communities, supporting livelihoods, food security, and cultural heritage worldwide. These benefits, however, are undermined by illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing, which the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) describes as “one of the greatest threats to marine ecosystems”.¹ Beyond depleting marine resources, IUU fishing distorts markets, disadvantages legal fishers, and weakens sustainable seafood supply chains. It is also frequently linked to wider criminal activity, including tax fraud,² money laundering,³ labor rights abuses,⁴ human trafficking, and the smuggling of drugs,⁵ arms, and wildlife products.^{6,7}

Key to combating IUU fishing is to identify the ‘beneficial owner’ of a fishing vessel: the individuals who ultimately own, control, and profit from fishing activities. Determining the beneficial owner is essential for effective deterrence and enforcement, but limited transparency in the global fisheries sector makes this very challenging.

Beneficial owners can hide their involvement by registering (“flagging”) vessels in countries unrelated to their residence or nationality, or by using complex corporate structures to evade scrutiny and sanctions. Opaque arrangements – such as shell companies, layered ownership, joint ventures, and frequent changes in vessel names and flags – enable beneficial owners to obscure their identities. This deliberate concealment distances them from liability and hinders both national and international enforcement efforts. Without visibility over beneficial ownership, authorities struggle to impose effective penalties, disrupt organized networks, or deter repeat offending.

This is where beneficial ownership transparency becomes critical. Beneficial ownership transparency refers to the identification and disclosure of the natural persons who ultimately own, control, or benefit from legal entities (such as companies) and legal arrangements (such as trusts). It is already used in other sectors to address a range of illicit activities, including money

laundering, corruption, tax evasion, and the financing of organized crime, and is increasingly recognized as a key transparency tool for tackling IUU fishing.⁸

Momentum for beneficial ownership transparency in fisheries is building. Open and accessible sharing of beneficial ownership information enables countries to manage their marine resources more sustainably and fairly, while allowing coastal communities and local fishers to identify the real owners behind fishing vessels. Collection of beneficial ownership information helps prevent hidden or foreign interests from monopolizing access to fishing grounds and allows regulators to screen and track individuals behind corporate entities, reducing the risk that offenders circumvent licensing restrictions or sanctions by re-entering the sector under new identities or through new corporate forms. What is now needed is sustained political will, stronger international and institutional coordination, and consistent implementation to apply these tools effectively across fisheries governance systems.

This briefing presents examples of how gathering beneficial ownership information can cut through complex corporate structures to identify those truly responsible for illegal fishing. By doing so, authorities can move beyond deliberate obfuscation and hold the real beneficiaries accountable.

Tracing the layers of a landmark IUU fishing case: from vessels to beneficial owners

In January 2015, a New Zealand patrol identified several fishing vessels – the *Kunlun* (IMO: 7322897), *Songhua* (IMO: 9319856), and *Yongding* (IMO: 9042001) – operating illegally in the Southern Ocean, an area managed by the Commission for the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources (CCAMLR), where 36 countries and the EU jointly regulate marine resources.⁹ These vessels were on CCAMLR’s official IUU fishing vessel list, prohibiting them, for example, from landing their catch in any member country.¹⁰ Investigations found that the vessels’ senior officers were Spanish nationals and that ownership was concealed through shell companies registered in Belize and Panama.^{10,11} This triggered a major Spanish investigation into a wider illegal fishing network linked to Spanish individuals and companies. Subsequent investigations revealed a covert global

operation harvesting high-value species in protected waters, with profits routed through complex corporate and financial structures linked back to Spain.¹¹ Based on the group’s estimated profits of €10 million in a single fishing season, authorities concluded that the group could have made €100 million over time.^{11,12}

Identifying those who benefited from these illegal fishing practices was a daunting task for both law enforcement and fishing authorities. The following strategies illustrate how those engaging in illegal fishing might obscure information that links individual vessels to those responsible for decision-making.

Vessel-level obfuscation strategy: renaming and flag hopping

One of the most common strategies for concealing vessel ownership involves frequent renaming and flag changes. The *Kunlun*, for instance, has changed its name 18 times and operated under nine different flags (see Figure 1).¹³ Similarly, the *Yongding* adopted at least 15 names and 12 flags over its operational lifetime.¹³ These changes were not incidental but formed part of a systematic strategy to disrupt continuity in monitoring and enforcement records.¹²

allowing them to escape fines for previous or repeat violations.¹⁴ In some cases, there might also be limited or no information exchange between the previous and new flag states, meaning that violations, sanctions, or inclusion on IUU fishing lists of Regional Fisheries Management Organizations may not follow the vessel across jurisdictions.¹⁵ The new flag state also may not systematically verify the vessel’s prior compliance history.

The practice of changing a vessel’s flag, commonly referred to as ‘flag hopping,’ enables vessels to effectively “reset” their regulatory identity – often

Figure 1. History of name and flag changes for the *Kunlun*.

Source: Trygg Mat Tracking.¹³

Vessel-level obfuscation strategy: flags of convenience

One of the core principles of international maritime law is that there must be a genuine link between a vessel and its flag state.¹⁶ However, this is not always enforced, particularly when fishing operators register their vessels under a flag of convenience (FoC). FoC states typically offer open registries, allowing vessel owners to register their vessels regardless of where the owner is based or their nationality.¹⁷ They often offer economic advantages such as lower tax rates, weak labor laws, and minimal administrative costs.¹⁷ FoCs can also be associated with weak fisheries monitoring, control, and surveillance mechanisms, as well as limited political or judicial will or capacity to enforce fisheries rules and ensure accountability.¹⁸ This often creates an environment that facilitates IUU fishing. Flag hopping is closely linked to the broader use of FoCs. The *Kunlun*, for example, was registered under the flags of five countries considered to be FoCs by the International Transport Workers' Federation (ITF).¹⁹ Because registration under FoCs is easy and oversight is weak, vessels may also frequently reflag between various FoCs to avoid scrutiny or sanctions.

The *Pilot Whale* (IMO: 7703986), a 100-metre-long pelagic trawler, has spent decades fishing along the West African coast, likely targeting small pelagic fishes such as sardinella, sardines, and mackerel.²⁰ Over time, it has fished under multiple flags, including those of Cameroon, Georgia, and Guinea-Bissau^a, all of which are considered FoC countries by ITF.¹⁹ Beyond its documented history of illegal fishing in Senegalese waters under the Russian flag and with Russian beneficial ownership,²¹ the vessel's operational history suggests that both its previous Russian owners and its current joint Latvian and Emirati owners have systematically used FoCs to evade surveillance and fisheries control measures in West African waters (see Figure 2).^b According to Global Fishing Watch and Lloyd's List Intelligence, since 2019, this vessel has been fishing in the waters of Mauritania and Guinea-Bissau under the flag of Cameroon, without ever having entered Cameroonian waters (see Figure 3).^c By registering with FoCs, beneficial owners can target increasingly overfished small pelagic fish stocks²² while bypassing stricter registration and reporting processes.

a. Flag state data were retrieved from Lloyd's List Intelligence database, [Seasearcher](#), [2026, May 8].

b. Vessel ownership data were retrieved from Lloyd's List Intelligence database, [Seasearcher](#), [2026, May 8]. The beneficial ownership information available in the Lloyd's List Intelligence database, [Seasearcher](#), may sometimes relate to companies, not natural persons. This information may differ from that regarding the ultimate beneficial owner (UBO), who is the individual (or sometimes a small group of individuals) who ultimately owns or exercises effective control over a legal entity.

c. AIS data were retrieved from Global Fishing Watch, [2026, May 8]. [Global Fishing Watch](#) is an international non-profit organization dedicated to advancing ocean governance through increased transparency of human activity at sea. The views and opinions expressed in this report are those of the authors, which are not connected with or sponsored, endorsed, or granted official status by Global Fishing Watch. By creating and publicly sharing map visualizations, data and analysis tools, Global Fishing Watch aims to enable scientific research and transform the way our ocean is managed. Global Fishing Watch's public data was used in the production of this publication. Any and all references to "fishing" should be understood in the context of Global Fishing Watch's fishing detection algorithm, which is a best effort to determine "apparent fishing effort" based on vessel speed and direction data from the Automatic Identification System (AIS) collected via satellites and terrestrial receivers. As AIS data varies in completeness, accuracy, and quality, and the fishing detection algorithm is a statistical estimate of apparent fishing activity, therefore it is possible that some fishing effort is not identified and conversely, that some fishing effort identified is not fishing. For these reasons, GFW qualifies all designations of vessel fishing effort, including synonyms of the term "fishing effort," such as "fishing" or "fishing activity," as "apparent," rather than certain. Any/all GFW information about "apparent fishing effort" should be considered an estimate and must be relied upon solely at your own risk. GFW is taking steps to make sure fishing effort designations are as accurate as possible.

The timeline of a single fishing vessel: *Pilot Whale*

SUMMARY	1992	1996	2002	2009	2013	2014	2019	2022	2024	
Vessel Name	Mikhail Verbitskiy				Pilot Whale	Mikhail Verbitskiy	Pilot Whale			
Flag	Russia				Saint Kitts and Nevis	Russia	Georgia	Cameroon	Guinea-Bissau	
Registered Owner	N/A	Sevrybpromrazvedka Prospecting & Scientific Research Fleet Administration	ZAO 'Karat-1'	Transco Company Limited	Inflex Group Corporation	Transco Company Limited	Ocean Whale Company Limited			
Beneficial Owner	Sevrybpoisk	Sevrybpromrazvedka Prospecting & Scientific Research Fleet Administration	N/A	Transco Company Limited	Inflex Group Corporation	Transco Company Limited	Denis Basin (50%) & Vladimir Sinelnikov (50%)	Bozena Basina (50%) & Sergejs Sinelnikovs (50%)	Bozena Basina (50%) (Lithuania) & Fish Fleet Management FZE (50%)	

Figure 2. The name, flag and ownership timeline of the *Pilot Whale*.

Source: Lloyd's List Intelligence.

Figure 3. *Pilot Whale* fishing activity in West African waters.

Source: Global Fishing Watch^c.

Corporate-level obfuscation strategy: shell companies, layered ownership and secrecy jurisdictions

At the corporate level, owners of vessels engaged in IUU fishing may also hide their true identities and activities behind complex company structures. One example is the use of shell companies: legal entities that typically exist only on paper, with no employees, operations, or physical presence. In such arrangements, the shell company often holds assets and manages financial transactions on behalf of a parent company, allowing control and profits to be separated from legal ownership and visible operational activity.²³

The Spanish investigation mentioned above uncovered that the network used shell companies established across multiple secrecy jurisdictions^d, including Belize and Panama.^{10,11} These jurisdictions have historically been characterized by limited transparency and disclosure requirements, although both countries have taken steps toward improving financial transparency regulations in recent years.^{24,25}

According to research by C4ADS, over 50% of IUU fishing networks use shell or front companies, highlighting the systemic nature of corporate opacity in illegal fishing operations.²⁶ Shell companies and secrecy jurisdictions not only allow beneficial owners to remain hidden behind multiple corporate layers but can also support the movement and laundering of illicit profits across jurisdictions, further distancing decision-makers from the underlying illegal activities. Secrecy jurisdictions chosen for the incorporation of shell companies would often be those where there is no requirement to register or update the legal or beneficial ownership of companies, where such information is not publicly accessible, and where the country does not have an exchange of information

agreement with the country of the beneficial owner – meaning the authorities cannot request information. Using such structures, vessels can be repeatedly bought, sold, or reassigned between interconnected companies, creating the appearance of changing ownership while effectively remaining under the control of the same underlying network (see, for example, Figure 4). This practice of changing apparent ownership generates layered legal and administrative opacity. By structuring transfers between related entities, fishing companies disrupt ownership continuity and significantly complicate the ability of enforcement authorities to trace responsibility or identify ultimate beneficiaries.

Figure 4. Fictional example for illustrative purposes of complex ownership structure and reselling practices.

The case of the *Fin Whale* (IMO: 8314299), a trawler from the same fleet as the *Pilot Whale*, is another example illustrating this obfuscation strategy. The *Fin Whale* has a similarly suspicious history of name changes and switching among FoCs. According to Lloyd's List, since 2022, it has been registered under the flags of Cameroon, Guinea-Bissau, and The Gambia, where it is currently flagged.^e As Figure 5 shows, while fishing in Mauritania under these three different FoCs, beneficial ownership and control of the *Fin Whale* was shared between a Lithuanian national and a company from the United Arab Emirates, whose owner could

not be identified.^e However, the vessel was operated by Ocean Whale Company Limited, a Maltese company that appears to be a shell company, according to the International Consortium of Investigative Journalists²⁷ and the Maltese Business Registry²⁸. Various layers of opacity like this can create an atmosphere in which fishing owners might avoid stricter fisheries rules, quotas, and scrutiny from their home country while their vessels continue to fish for overexploited small pelagic fishes in West Africa²⁹.

d. Secrecy jurisdictions are territories, including cities, states, provinces and countries that encourage the relocation of otherwise foreign economic and financial transactions through strong privacy protection rules. These jurisdictions ensure that the identity of those relocating their money through them cannot be disclosed. This often undermines legislation and regulation of another jurisdiction. Many secrecy jurisdictions are also tax havens.

e. Vessel ownership data were retrieved from Lloyd's List Intelligence database, [Seasearcher](#), [2026, May 8]. Data may contain errors, meaning that ownership should only be presumed.

Figure 5. Map with fishing activity, flag states, registered owners and beneficial owners of the *Fin Whale*.

Source: Global Fishing Watch^c and Lloyd's List Intelligence.

Another common strategy is for beneficial owners to maintain control through intermediary companies, legally distancing beneficial owners from the vessels engaged in illegal fishing. Figure 6 provides an fictional example of such a layered structure. Multiple layers of foreign shell companies are frequently inserted between the vessels

engaged in illegal fishing and the individuals directing and benefiting from the operations. This diffusion of liability allows those at the top of an IUU fishing network to maintain effective control while denying involvement in the vessels' illegal activities¹³.

Figure 6. Fictional example for illustrative purposes of corporate ownership structure of fishing vessels.

Financial and legal obfuscation strategy: bearer shares

Further opacity can be created through financial and legal arrangements designed to conceal ownership and diffuse liability. Bearer shares are a type of financial instrument where an individual “owns” a legal interest in a corporation solely by virtue of possessing a physical share certificate, and does not appear as a registered owner in the company’s records.³⁰ Because there is no official registry linking a specific individual or entity to the shares, whoever “bears” the certificate is legally presumed to hold ownership in that company, which can then be transferred simply by handing over the certificate. This anonymity has historically

made bearer shares attractive for secrecy and a major obstacle to transparency.³⁰

In the context of IUU fishing violations, they can be used to obscure the true beneficial owners of vessels and operating companies. This hinders the ability of fisheries authorities and law enforcement agencies to trace responsibility and enforce penalties. As shown in Figure 7 with a fictional example, shares in the Belize-registered shell entity were issued as bearer shares. By layering companies across jurisdictions and issuing bearer shares, the individuals who ultimately control fishing operations can remain hidden.

Figure 7. Fictional example for illustrative purposes of a vessel's ownership structure and use of bearer shares.

Conclusions and recommendations

The strategies described above demonstrate how illegal fishing can be deliberately concealed through complex, transnational corporate structures. In such circumstances, vessel-level or at-sea enforcement alone is insufficient to hold the true perpetrators to account.

These cases also illustrate the unique value of beneficial ownership analysis as both a law enforcement and accountability tool. In the Spanish investigation, tracing ownership and control across multiple corporate entities and jurisdictions made it possible to unveil the scale and systematic nature of the violations in the Spanish investigation, ultimately resulting in fines of approximately €17.8 million.¹¹ Furthermore, the beneficial owners were disqualified from conducting fishing operations and obtaining public subsidies and other benefits.¹¹ Crucially, beneficial ownership data enabled authorities to move beyond individual vessels to identify repeated and coordinated illegal fishing activity, aggregate sanctions across related vessels, and determine where effective control and decision-making actually resided. This shift made it possible to direct enforcement actions toward those

who orchestrated and profited from illegal fishing activities, rather than those physically present on board the vessel.

While beneficial ownership analysis ultimately enabled investigators to unravel these cases, the process would have been far quicker and more straightforward if the countries involved had collected beneficial ownership data or had a national beneficial ownership registry in place. Access to such beneficial ownership data or a registry that includes fishing vessels would have enabled authorities to rapidly identify the individuals behind layered companies and share that information with international counterparts.

The central lesson of these cases is clear: illegal fishing cannot be effectively addressed without transparency regarding who ultimately owns, controls, and benefits from those vessels and their operations. Robust collection and meaningful transparency of beneficial ownership data are therefore indispensable to combating IUU fishing and ensuring that sanctions are proportionate, adequately deterrent, and directed at the true perpetrators.

Oceana calls upon countries to:

- **Require and verify legal and beneficial ownership information at the time of flagging or when allowing access to their waters.** All flag and coastal states should collect and verify legal and beneficial ownership information for all fishing vessels at the time of vessel registration, flagging, or when issuing authorizations to fish in their waters.
- **Publish and maintain public lists of authorized vessels fishing under their flag or operating in their waters.** Ensure access to associated beneficial ownership information and comply with beneficial ownership disclosure obligations of regional fisheries bodies.
- **Require their citizens, and the companies incorporated in their jurisdiction, to disclose any legal, beneficial, or financial interests they hold in fishing vessels flagged to foreign countries.** All states should collect and make this information public.
- **Use multiple channels to collect and verify beneficial ownership information, including through vessel registration, fishing license issuance, company incorporation, and financial and insurance sectors.** Self-declaration by beneficial owners and cross-checks with national ownership registries should be standard practice, supported by anti-money laundering frameworks.
- **Share information with relevant authorities.** Where a national beneficial ownership registry already exists, fisheries and transport ministries should be able to access and cross-reference this information.

References

- 1 Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (n.d.). *Illegal, unreported and unregulated (IUU) fishing*. <https://www.fao.org/iuu-fishing/en/>
- 2 Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2013). *Evading the Net: Tax Crime in the Fisheries Sector*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/933849b5-en>
- 3 Asia/Pacific Group on Money Laundering. (2023). *APG Issues Paper: Illicit financial flows generated from illegal fishing*. https://apgml.org/sites/default/files/documents/APG_Issues_Paper_-_Illicit_financial_flows_generated_from_illegal_fishing_-_November_2023.pdf
- 4 Decker Sparks, J. L., & Hasche, L. K. (2019). Complex linkages between forced labor slavery and environmental decline in marine fisheries. *Journal of Human Rights*, 18(2), 230- 245. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14754835.2019.1602824>
- 5 United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2011). *Transnational organized crime in the fishing industry*. United Nations. https://www.unodc.org/documents/human-trafficking/Issue_Paper_-_TOC_in_the_Fishing_Industry.pdf
- 6 Wyatt, T. (2021). *Wildlife trafficking: A deconstruction of the crime, the victims, and the offenders*. Springer Nature. <https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137269249>
- 7 Haenlein, C. (2017). *Below the surface: How illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing threatens our security*. Royal United Services Institute. https://static.rusi.org/201707_rusi_below_the_surface_haenlein.pdf
- 8 Rossi, I., El Khoury, C. A., Thomas, I., Malcherek, L., & Al Janahi, M. (2025). *Targeted transparency: Sectoral approach to beneficial ownership in procurement and real estate*. IMF Working Papers No. 181. International Monetary Fund. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9798229023832.001>
- 9 New Zealand Government. (2015, January 14). *Further illegal fishing vessel discovered* [Press release]. <https://www.beehive.govt.nz/release/further-illegal-fishing-vessel-discovered>
- 10 Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC). (2015, April 18). *Complementary elements for discussion under item 7 of the agenda for the Compliance Committee*. IOTC-2015-CoC12-08a Rev4[E]. IOTC Secretariat. <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/b63b20f2-f056-442d-a2b1-5deaca5ce933/content>
- 11 ClientEarth. (2019). *The Spanish legal process for prosecuting illegal fishing: A story of success?* <https://www.clientearth.org/media/cd0jgn3j/the-spanish-legal-process-for-prosecuting-illegal-fishing-a-story-of-success-ce-en.pdf>
- 12 Interpol. (2016, March 18). *Spanish operation nets suspects behind illegal fishing*. <https://www.interpol.int/en/News-and-Events/News/2016/Spanish-operation-nets-suspects-behind-illegal-fishing>
- 13 Trygg Mat Tracking. (n.d.). *Vessel Details - ASIAN WARRIOR - Currently Listed*. Combined IUU Vessel List. <https://www.iuu-vessels.org/Vessel/GetVessel/40e28ac4-d7e6-47a8-8f3b-ed8100442105>
- 14 European Court of Auditors. (2026). *EU action to combat illegal fishing control systems in place but weakened by uneven checks and sanctions by Member States*. https://www.eca.europa.eu/lists/ecadocuments/sr22_20/sr_illegal_fishing_en.pdf
- 15 Hutniczak, B. (2019). *Coordination between RFMOs on mutual recognition of IUU vessel lists*. *Marine Policy*, 107, 103596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.103596>
- 16 United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, December 10, 1982, 1833 U.N.T.S. 397 (entered into force Nov. 16, 1994), https://www.un.org/depts/los/convention_agreements/texts/unclos/unclos_e.pdf
- 17 European Commission: European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency, Schinas, O., Progoulaki, M., Hallside, M., Myti, M., Petidou, V., & Danckwerts, O. (2026). *Study on flag State responsibilities and 'open registers' for vessel registration*. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2926/1253552>
- 18 Oceana. (2026). *Flags of convenience and hidden ownership: EU-owned fishing vessels in high-risk jurisdictions*. <https://europe.oceana.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/26/2026/01/Report-flags-of-convenience-2026.pdf>
- 19 International Transport Workers' Federation. (n.d.). *Current registries listed as FOCs*. <https://www.itfseafarers.org/en/issues/flags-of-convenience/current-registries-listed-focs>
- 20 Oceana. (2025). *Why transparency matters: Exposing EU ownership of high-risk fishing vessels in Guinea-Bissau*. <https://europe.oceana.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/26/2025/02/BRIEFING-WHY-TRANSPARENCY-MATTERS-GUINEA-BISSAU.pdf>
- 21 Greenpeace. (2012). *Main basse sur la Sardine. Le scandale des autorisations de pêche au Sénégal: un drame en cinq actes*. Greenpeace Africa. https://www.greenpeace.ch/static/planet4-switzerland-stateless/2019/05/994a93a1-994a93a1-2012_oceans_rapport_mainsardine.pdf
- 22 Failler, P. (2024). *Small Pelagics in West Africa face the multiple challenges of food security, wealth creation and regional governance*. *Marine Policy*, 170, 106374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106374>
- 23 Global Financial Integrity. (n.d.). *Anonymous Shell Companies*. <https://gfintegrity.org/issue/anonymous-shell-companies/>
- 24 Caribbean Financial Action Task Force. (2025). *Anti-money laundering and counter-terrorist financing measures - Belize, Mutual Evaluation Report*. <https://www.fatf-gafi.org/content/dam/fatf-gafi/frsb-mer/Belize-MER-2024.pdf.coredownload.inline.pdf>
- 25 International Monetary Fund. (2024). *Panama: Financial Sector Assessment Program - Technical Note on Anti-Money Laundering and Combating the Financing of Terrorism (AML/CFT)*. IMF Country Report No. 24/234. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9798400284762.002>
- 26 C4ADS. (2019). *Strings Attached: Exploring the Onshore Networks Behind Illegal, Unreported & Unregulated Fishing*. <https://c4ads.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/StringsAttached-Report.pdf>
- 27 International Consortium of Investigative Journalists. (n.d.). *Offshore leaks database: Node 55074402*. Retrieved 22 April 2026 from <https://offshoreleaks.icij.org/nodes/55074402>
- 28 Maltese Business Registry. (2024). *Ocean Whale Company Limited*. <https://europe.oceana.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/26/2025/01/Malta-Ocean-Whale-Involved-parties.pdf>
- 29 Tournon-Gardic, G., Hermansen, Ø., Failler, P., Dia, A.D., Tarbia, M.O.L., Brahim, K., Thorpe, A., Deme, E.H.B., Beibou, E., Abou Kane, E. & Bouzouma, M. (2022). *The small pelagics value chain in Mauritania - Recent changes and food security impacts*. *Marine Policy*, 143, 105190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2022.105190>
- 30 FATF. (2023). *Beneficial ownership of legal persons*. <https://www.fatf-gafi.org/content/dam/fatf-gafi/guidance/Guidance-Beneficial-Ownership-Legal-Persons.pdf.coredownload.pdf>

Suggested citation: Kasana, D., Knobel, A., Rosado Y., Skerritt, D., Vulperhorst, V. (2026). *Hidden owners, hidden crimes: Why beneficial ownership transparency matters for fisheries enforcement*. Oceana. 8 pp.

DOI Number: 10.5281/zenodo.20328883

Photos and illustrations: © OCEANA.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.